

D1.2:

Systematic review of validated instruments for measuring research misconduct and questionable research practices

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1.	Coordinator	University of Oslo	UiO	Norway
2.	Partner	European Network of Research Ethics Committees	EUREC	Belgium
3.	Partner	High Council For The Evaluation of Research and Higher Education	HCERES	France
4.	Partner	French Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment	INRAE	France
5.	Partner	Oslo Metropolitan University	OsloMet	Norway
6.	Partner	Eurosis Federation of Finnish Learned Societies	TSV	Finland
7.	Partner	University of Central Lancashire-Cyprus	UCLanCY	Cyprus
8.	Partner	University of Helsinki	UH	Finland
9.	Partner	University of Humanistic Studies	UHS	The Netherlands
10.	Partner	University of Latvia	UL	Latvia
11.	Partner	University of Tartu	UTARTU	Estonia
12.	Partner	Stichting VUMC / The Embassy of Good Science	VUMC	The Netherlands
13.	AP	Trilateral Research LTD	TRI	UK
14.	AP	Heriot-Watt University	HWU	SCT

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1. Background

The purpose of this systematic review is to identify, and quality assess validated instruments used in the literature to measure aspects of research misconduct and/or questionable research practices (QRP).

One of the most common methods used to quantify aspects of research misconduct or QRP in a defined population of researchers or research students is the survey. These surveys may measure diverse properties such as the incidence of research misconduct or QRP, attitudes towards research misconduct or QRP, or knowledge about guidelines.

In order to measure any of these properties accurately it is important to use well-validated questions and instruments. Using already validated instruments will also enable better comparisons between different studies and will make any future use of data in meta-analysis more straightforward. As an example, incidence rates for self-reported research misconduct can only be directly compared if the questions that respondents have answered are phrased in an identical manner. It is therefore important for researchers in the field to identify validated instruments they can use in their surveys.

2. Methodology

A systematic review protocol following the PRISMA guidelines was developed and deposited at the Open Science Framework repository prior to the review commencing (Eriksen 2022). This protocol was followed throughout the review process¹.

2.1 Search strategy

Inclusion criteria:

- Studies that validate research misconduct or QRP survey instruments aimed at a population of researchers (including PhD students)
- All study types
- All years

Exclusion criteria:

- Application studies (studies that have not developed or validated an instrument)
- Studies that investigate only a population of students (apart from PhD students)
- Studies on non-validated instruments

¹ Text from this protocol reused in this report will not be set in quotation marks or specifically referenced to the protocol.

- Non-English, except -Danish, -Norwegian, -Swedish, -German, -French, -Italian, -Spanish, or -Dutch language publications, irrespective of whether the instrument developed and/or validated is in one of these languages²

Information sources:

Medline (OVID), PsycINFO (OVID), Scopus (Elsevier) and Academic Search Premier (EBSCO) were searched. We searched both subject headings and free text search terms, when possible. No date restriction was implied. Information regarding presented instruments was tracked by browsing relevant websites if necessary, e.g. to identify the availability of an instrument.

Table 1. Medline Search Parameters

1	Scientific Misconduct/
2	Plagiarism/
3	Ethics, Research/
4	((Research* or Academic* or Scientific or scientist*) adj2 (misconduct or fraud or malpractice* or dishonest* or integrity or decision making or misbehavi* or cheat*)) or (ethical adj2 (research* or scienti*) adj2 (conduct* or behavi*)) or (Questionable adj2 research adj2 practice*) or (Questionable adj2 research adj2 behavior) or (Questionable adj2 research adj2 behaviour*) or ((Fabricat* or falsif*) adj2 (data or result* or image*)) or Plagiari* or (Responsible adj2 research adj2 practice*) or (Responsible adj2 conduct adj2 research) or research ethics or data irreproducibility or data reproducibility or reproducible research or (reproducibility adj2 research)).mp.
5	1 or 2 or 3 or 4 (research misconduct)
6	"Surveys and Questionnaires"/
7	Pilot Projects/
8	6 and 7
9	(Develop* or Test* or Pilot* or valid* or verify* or substanti* or reliab*).mp
10	6 and 9
11	(Survey* or Question* or Scale* or Instrument* or tool*).mp.
12	7 and 11
13	((Survey* or Question* or Scale* or Instrument* or tool*) adj10 (Develop* or Test* or Pilot*

² To reduce the epistemic injustice caused by language exclusions the research group included papers on all languages that at least one member of the group can read.

	or valid* or substanti* or reliab*).mp.
14	8 or 10 or 12 or 13
15	5 and 14

This Medline search was translated to the other databases.

2.2 Review process

The review process was implemented in COVIDENCE (covidence.org). The initial abstract screening was performed independently by two reviewers, and disagreements resolved in a group meeting involving all collaborators. The same process was followed for full text screening. Quality assessment was performed independently by two reviewers, and disagreement resolved between reviewers. Data extraction was performed by one collaborator and validated by another collaborator.

2.3 Quality assessment

There is no specific quality assessment tool for instruments measuring aspects of research misconduct or QRP. The quality assessment has therefore been performed using the most relevant extant quality assessment tool, i.e. the COSMIN framework for assessing patient outcome measurement instruments (Mokkink et al 2010, COSMIN). COSMIN has been developed further since the original publication and the most recent version is the web-version (COSMIN). The development processes and the steps taken to assess psychometric validity are relatively underdeveloped in relation to instruments measuring aspects of research misconduct or QRP when compared to the state of the art for patient outcome measurement instruments, and the simplified COSMIN-derived checklist developed by Francis et al have therefore been used in this study (Francis et al 2016). This checklist contains 18 items. The checklist is aimed at the quality assessment of patient reported outcome (PRO) measures and 3 of the items are not relevant to research misconduct or QRP measures and were not used in the present review (Table 1).

In relation to the development of instruments measuring aspects of research misconduct or QRP the distinction between item 4 and item 5 in the checklist is potentially ambiguous. The instruments are usually developed by research integrity content experts (item 5), who are also potentially members of the respondent population (item 4); or the members of the respondent population that are involved in the development are at the same time content experts. We have scored these two criteria as both met, if people from outside the development group itself have been involved in the development of the measure. Methodologically it would be preferable if 'naive' members of the respondent population, i.e. researchers who do not work or publish on research misconduct or QRP, are involved in the development of the instrument.

Given that research misconduct and QRP are recognised as problematic behaviours there is a significant risk of respondents showing social desirability bias in their responses. This can be mitigated to some extent by ensuring anonymity, and we thus added an item related to whether the validation study was anonymous (item 19).

Items were scored as 'Criterion met' / 'Criterion partly met' / 'Criterion not met', with an additional category of 'Not applicable' for items 9 and 11-13.

An instrument is classified as well-validated if the conceptual model (item 1), testing for reliability (item 7 & 8), and scoring and interpretation information (item 13) was scored as 'Criterion met' in the quality assessment.

Table 2. Quality assessment criteria (modified from Francis et. al. 2016)

<p>Conceptual model</p> <p>1. Has the research misconduct or QRP construct to be measured been specifically defined?</p> <p>2. Has the intended respondent population been described?</p> <p>3. Does the conceptual model address whether a single construct/scale or multiple subscales are expected?</p> <p>Content validity</p> <p>4. Is there evidence that members of the intended respondent population were involved in the measure's development?</p> <p>5. Is there evidence that content experts were involved in the measure's development?</p> <p>6. Is there a description of the methodology by which items / questions were determined (e.g., focus groups, interviews)?</p> <p>Reliability</p> <p>7. Is there evidence that the measure's reliability was tested (e.g., test-retest, internal consistency)?</p> <p>8. Are reported indices of reliability adequate (e.g., ideal: $r \geq 0.80$; adequate: $r \geq 0.70$), or otherwise justified?</p> <p>Construct validity</p> <p>9. Is there reported quantitative justification that single scale or multiple subscales exist in the measure (e.g., factor analysis, item response theory)?</p> <p>10. Are there findings supporting expected associations with existing PRO measures or with other relevant data?</p> <p>11. Are there findings supporting expected differences in scores between relevant known groups?</p> <p>Scoring & interpretation</p> <p>12. Is the PRO measure intended to measure change over time? If YES, is there evidence of both test-retest reliability AND responsiveness to change? Otherwise, is there an explicit statement that the PRO measure is NOT intended to measure change over time.</p> <p>13. Is there documentation how to score the PRO measure (e.g., scoring method such as summing or an algorithm)?</p> <p>14. Has a plan for managing and/or interpreting missing responses been described (i.e., how to score incomplete surveys)?</p> <p>15. Item not applicable (Is information provided about how to interpret the PRO measure scores [e.g. scaling/anchors, (what high and low scores represent), normative data, and/or a definition of severity (mild -> severe)]?)</p> <p>Presentation</p> <p>16. Item not applicable (Is the time to complete reported and reasonable? OR, if it is NOT reported, is the number of questions appropriate for the intended application?)</p> <p>17. Item not applicable (Is there a description of the literacy level of the PRO measure?)</p> <p>18. Is the entire measure available for public viewing (e.g., published with the citation, or information provided about how to access a copy)?</p> <p>19. Item added: In this study, could people answer anonymously?</p>
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3. Results

The review process is reported in the PRISMA flowsheet in Appendix A. A total of 48 studies were finally included for data extraction. The full list of references for these studies is in Appendix B. This includes 32 studies of instruments leading to a validated scale or set of scales, and 16 studies of validated questionnaires not leading to a scale. Here we report the results for the validated instruments leading to a scale only. For some instruments more than one relevant study is included, and some studies investigate more than one scale. Based on the quality assessment the instruments are divided into well-validated scales (Table 3) and less-well-validated scales (Table 4).

4. Discussion and conclusions

This systematic review of validated instruments for measuring responsible conduct of research indicates that the field currently shows quite varied methodological sophistication and rigour. The development and validation processes are, in many cases not reflective of best practice in psychometrics (COSMIN, Rust et al 2021). This is perhaps not surprising since many instruments seem to be developed by research integrity experts without involvement of experts in scale development. Many instruments are initially developed with input from only the researchers themselves, or the researchers and a few research integrity experts, but without input from persons with domain expertise and experience. The psychometric validation is often also rather perfunctory, relying only on the calculation of Cronbach's alpha (Cronbach 1951), and finding a satisfactory value of alpha. All instruments identified have been statistically validated using classical test theory, and none are validated using item-response theory (Rust et al 2021).

Most of the instruments have been developed within a biomedical context, and apart from instruments measuring attitudes toward plagiarism no instruments have been identified that measure aspects of research misconduct or QRP within the humanities or other research areas that are not primarily data-driven. There may be instruments developed within the humanities that have not been captured by the search strategy, but the research group has extensive knowledge of the field and are not aware of any.

There is thus a need for the development of new scales using state of the art development and validation processes.

The systematic review shows that there are reasonably well-validated scales measuring:

- Attitudes towards plagiarism (Mavrinac et al 2010)
- Attitudes towards research misconduct (Holm & Hofmann 2017, 2018)
- Perceptions of research misconduct (Broome et al 2005)
- Self-reported research misconduct and questionable research practices (Tijdink et al 2016, Wester et al 2008)
- Organisational research climate (Martinson et al 2013, Solomon et al 2022)

It would make comparisons of results between scientific fields, institutions and countries simpler and more accurate if researchers considered using these instruments in their surveys, instead of developing their own.

It would also be helpful if any new instruments were developed following best practices in psychometrics, including all of the following steps (for further elaboration of best practice see Rust et al 2021, Ranganathan et al 2023 & 2024):

- Explicit definition of conceptual model and concept(s) to be measured
- Initial development of question pool with involvement of experts and intended respondent group
- Testing for content validity with experts and intended respondent group
- Initial testing and selection of questions from initial question pool
- Comprehensive testing for reliability
- Comprehensive testing for construct validity

Table 3. Well-validated instruments

Scale name - if named *	Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Validation respondent group(s)	Statistical validation method(s)	Quality of development	Quality of statistical validation	References	Availability
	Attitudes towards responsible conduct in research	21	5 point Likert scale	1. Attitudes toward the acceptability of RCR practices 2. General attitudes towards scientific misconduct	English	Researchers	Researchers, doctoral students, senior undergraduate students, research technicians	Exploratory factor analysis Cronbach's alpha Concurrent validity with RMSS	High	High	Abd ElHafeez et al 2022	Fully described in paper
	Stated as: Experiences, behaviors, and perceptions regarding research ethics But, example items in	35	Various	1. Ethics in research 2. Encountered research misconduct during the course of one's	Not stated, presumably Hebrew	Nurses	Nurses	Cronbach's alpha	Adequate	Adequate	Asman et al 2019	Not known

Scale name - if named *	Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Validation on respondent group(s)	Statistical validation method(s)	Quality of development	Quality of statistical validation	References	Availability
	paper indicate that 'research ethics' is understood as 'research integrity'			academic studies 3. The inclination to fabricate data 4. The inclination to select or omit data, and 5. Knowledge of research misconduct in the workplace								
Scientific Misconduct Questionnaire-Revised SMQ-R	Perceptions of the prevalence of different types of scientific misconduct	46 closed-choice 12 open-ended	Various 3 & 4 point Likert	1. Perception of Workplace Environment	English	Research coordinators of clinical trials	Research coordinators of clinical trials	Exploratory factor analysis Confirmatory factor analysis	High	High	Broome et al 2005	https://www.mededportal.org/doi/10.15766/mep_2374-8265.9593

Scale name - if named *	Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Validation respondent group(s)	Statistical validation method(s)	Quality of development	Quality of statistical validation	References	Availability
	and of factors that influence the occurrence of misconduct.	Developed from the Scientific Misconduct Questionnaire SMQ	scales	2. Prevalence of Scientific Misconduct 3. Awareness of Scientific Misconduct 4. Reporting Scientific Misconduct 5. Attitudes and Beliefs 6. Behavioral Influences 7. Experiences				Discriminant validity Cronbach's alpha				

Scale name - if named *	Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Validation respondent group(s)	Statistical validation method(s)	Quality of development	Quality of statistical validation	References	Availability
				es with Scientific Misconduct in Research (Open-ended questions)								
Scientific Misconduct Questionnaire SMQ	Perceptions of scientific misconduct	32	3,4,5 point Likert scales	1. Institutional Climate 2. Prevalence of Misconduct 3. Value and Attitude 4. Behavioral Influence	English	Nursing researchers	Nursing researchers	Confirmatory factor analysis Cronbach's alpha	High	High	Rankin & Esteves 1997	Partially described in paper

Scale name - if named *	Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Validation respondent group(s)	Statistical validation method(s)	Quality of development	Quality of statistical validation	References	Availability
Persian Research Misconduct Questionnaire PRMQ	Combination of SMQ-R and the Publication Pressure Questionnaire PPQ Translated to Farsi/Persian Some items removed in content validation process	63	Various	1. Perception of workplace Environment 2. Prevalence of scientific misconduct 3. Awareness of research misconduct 4. Reporting research misconduct 5. Beliefs about research misconduct	Farsi/Persian	Medical researchers	Medical researchers	Cronbach's alpha	High	Adequate	Shamsoddin et al 2020	Not known Link no longer functional https://forms.gle/LGp85PqvFQjbXzcUA

Scale name - if named *	Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Validation respondent group(s)	Statistical validation method(s)	Quality of development	Quality of statistical validation	References	Availability
				6. Behavioral influences 7. Publication pressure								
How I think about Research HIT-Res	Compliance disengagement in research Developed from the How I think (HIT) questionnaire	45	6 point Likert scale	1. Cognitive distortions 2. Anomalous responding	English	Medical researchers	Medical researchers	Cronbach's alpha Concurrent validity with measures of moral disengagement, cynicism, and professional decision-making in research	High	High	DuBois et al 2016	Fully described in paper
	Moral stress, moral	110	4 point	1. Moral stress in research	English	Medical	Medical researchers	Cronbach's alpha	Adequate	Adequate	Fisher et al 2013	Available from the first author upon request

Scale name - if named *	Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Validation respondent group(s)	Statistical validation method(s)	Quality of development	Quality of statistical validation	References	Availability
	practice, and ethical climate		Likert scale	2. organizational ethics climate 3. staff support 4. moral practice dilemmas in research 5. research commitment 6. research mistrust		researchers						
	Knowledge about definitions of research misconduct Perceived reasons for	24	Various	1. Knowledge about definitions of research misconduct	Chinese	Nurses	Nurses in tertiary hospitals	Cronbach's alpha	Adequate	Adequate	Han et al 2023	Available in supplementary data (in English)

Scale name - if named *	Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Validation respondent group(s)	Statistical validation method(s)	Quality of development	Quality of statistical validation	References	Availability
	research misconduct Perceived consequences of research misconduct			2. Perceived reasons for research misconduct 3. Perceived consequences of research misconduct								
	Perceived frequency and impact of research misbehaviors	20 randomly drawn from list of 60	3 point scale for frequency 5 point Likert scale for impact		English	Researchers	Researchers	Generalizability coefficient	Adequate	Adequate	Haven et al 2021	https://surfdrive.surf.nl/files/index.php/s/rhEAWrUap69jQ6a

Scale name - if named *	Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Validation respondent group(s)	Statistical validation method(s)	Quality of development	Quality of statistical validation	References	Availability
Kalichman's "Survey 2: Research Misconduct" Questionnaire	Attitudes towards research misconduct	14	5 point Likert scale	1. General attitude to misconduct 2. Attitude to personal misconduct 3. Attitude to whistle-blowing 4. Attitude to blameworthiness / punishment	English	Researchers and doctoral students	Doctoral students at medical faculties	Exploratory factor analysis Confirmatory factor analysis Cronbach's alpha Convergent validity with RMSS	Adequate	High	Holm & Hofmann 2017 & 2018	Fully described in Holm & Hofmann 2017
	Attitudes towards research ethics	15	5 point Likert scale	1. Attitudes toward	English	Medical researchers	Medical researchers	Cronbach's alpha	Adequate	Adequate	Kandee l et al 2011	Fully described in paper

Scale name - if named *	Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Validation respondent group(s)	Statistical validation method(s)	Quality of development	Quality of statistical validation	References	Availability
				research ethics 2. Attitudes toward research ethics committees								
	Ethical perceptions with regard to various research and publication behaviors	19 items, Each answered in relation to 4 separate sub-questions	7 point Likert scale for sub-scale 2 & 4	1. Have you ever witnessed the behavior firsthand? 2. How do you rate the behavior? 3. If you witnessed the behavior, what did you do about it? 4. If, in the	English	University-based health educators	University-based health educators	Test-retest	Adequate	Adequate	Kattenbraker 2008	Fully described in thesis

Scale name - if named *	Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Validation on respondent group(s)	Statistical validation method(s)	Quality of development	Quality of statistical validation	References	Availability
				future, you ever witness the behavior, how likely will you be to report the behavior?								
Survey of Organizational Research Climate SORC Now renamed SOuRCe	Organisational research climate	28 + 4 items about global perception of institution and department	5 point Likert scale + 'No basis for judging' option	1. Institutional Regulatory Quality 2. Institutional RCR Resources 3. Dept / Prog Integrity Norms 4. Dept / Prog	English	Health researchers	Health researchers	Exploratory factor analysis Confirmatory factor analysis Cronbach's alpha Discriminative validity Test-retest	High	High	Martinson et al 2013	Fully described in paper

Scale name - if named *	Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Validation respondent group(s)	Statistical validation method(s)	Quality of development	Quality of statistical validation	References	Availability
				Socialization 5. Dept / Prog Integrity Inhibitors 6. Dept / Prog Advisor-Advisee Relations 7. Dept / Prog Expectations				Convergent validity with perception of organizational justice				
Lab Climate for Research Ethics	Lab climate Very short version of SOuRCe	3	5 point Likert scale		English	Post-docs in health research	Post-docs in health research	Cronbach's alpha Convergent validity with SOuRCe sub-scales	High	High	Solomon et al 2022	Fully described in paper
Investigation of Questionable Authors	Reasons for and attitudes toward questionable	19	5 point Likert scale	1. Possible reasons for students	Mandarin Chinese	Researchers	Researchers	Exploratory factor analysis	Adequate	Adequate	Pan & Chou 2020	Fully described in paper (in English)

Scale name - if named *	Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Validation on respondent group(s)	Statistical validation method(s)	Quality of development	Quality of statistical validation	References	Availability
hip in Taiwan IQAT	authorship practices (QAPs)			1-1 Academic accomplishment 1-2 Academic convention 2. Possible reasons for research associates 2-1 Research accomplishment 2-2 Social function 3. Attitudes toward QAPs 3-1 Prevalence of								

Scale name - if named *	Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Validation respondent group(s)	Statistical validation method(s)	Quality of development	Quality of statistical validation	References	Availability
				misbehavior 3-2 Reputational harm								
Ethical practices in research	Part of much larger questionnaire with many sub-parts measuring aspects of ethics in health care institutions	9	4 point Likert scale		English	Researchers in health care institutions	Researchers in health care institutions	Inter-item correlation Test-retest	High	Adequate	Pearlman et al 2013	Described in paper, but one of the items is proprietary so not stated in full
	Knowledge, attitude and practice toward plagiarism	27	Various 3 point Likert scale for sub-scale 2	1. Knowledge of plagiarism 2. Attitude toward plagiarism 3. Practice	Unknown, probably Farsi/Persian	Bioethical researchers and students who have participated in at least	Biomedical researchers and students	Cronbach's alpha	Adequate	Adequate	Poorolajal et al 2012	Not known

Scale name - if named *	Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Validation respondent group(s)	Statistical validation method(s)	Quality of development	Quality of statistical validation	References	Availability
				of plagiarism		one research project						
Uses modified versions of two prior questionnaires. Both prior questionnaires originally developed to measure knowledge and attitudes in students	Knowledge and attitudes towards plagiarism	10 + 29	Various 5 point Likert scale for subscale 2	1. Knowledge of plagiarism 2. Attitudes towards Plagiarism Questionnaire (ATPQ)	English	Junior faculty members in medical colleges	Junior faculty members in medical colleges	Predicted difference between government and private colleges	Adequate	Adequate	Raj et al 2021	In original publications: 1. How to Recognize Plagiarism: Tutorials and Tests https://plagiarism.iu.edu/ 2. Mavrinac, M., Brumini, G., Bilić-Zulle, L., & Petrovečki, M. (2010). Construction and validation of attitudes toward plagiarism questionnaire. <i>Croatian medical journal</i> , 51(3), 195-201.
Uses modified version	Attitudes toward plagiarism	25	3 point		English	Faculty members and	Faculty members and	Confirmatory factor analysis	Adequate	Adequate	Rathore et al 2015	Fully described in paper

Scale name - if named *	Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Validation respondent group(s)	Statistical validation method(s)	Quality of development	Quality of statistical validation	References	Availability
of the Attitudes towards plagiarism questionnaire (ATPQ), originally developed to measure attitudes in students			Likert scale			students in medical colleges	students in medical colleges	(found different factor structure than in original study (Mavrillac et al 2010)) Cronbach's alpha				
Farsi/Persian version of the Attitudes toward plagiarism questionnaire (ATPQ), originally	Attitudes toward plagiarism	26	5 point Likert scale		Farsi/Persian	Researchers	Medical science post-graduate students and faculty members	Exploratory factor analysis Confirmatory factor analysis (found different factor structure than in	High	High	Tajalli et al 2022	Not known

Scale name - if named *	Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Validation respondent group(s)	Statistical validation method(s)	Quality of development	Quality of statistical validation	References	Availability
Developed to measure attitudes in students								original study (Mavrinac et al 2010)) Discriminant validity Cronbach's alpha				
	Knowledge and attitudes about issues in publication ethics	5 + 7	11 point Likert scale (Scale 1) 3 point Likert scale (Scale 2)	1. Perceived level of unethical behaviour 2. Perceived level of knowledge		Biomedical authors	Biomedical authors	Cronbach's alpha	High	High	Schroter et al 2018	Online In Supplementary file 1 https://bmjopen.bmj.com/content/bmjopen/8/11/e021282/DC1/embed/inline-supplementary-material-1.pdf?download=true
Research Misbehaviour	Self-reported research misconduct and	22	5 point Likert scale		English	Biomedical researchers	Biomedical researchers	Convergent validity with Machiavellianism	Adequate	Adequate	Tijdink et al 2016	Fully described in paper

Scale name - if named *	Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Validation respondent group(s)	Statistical validation method(s)	Quality of development	Quality of statistical validation	References	Availability
Severity Score RMSS	questionable research practice							Convergent validity with Kalichman attitude scale (Holm & Hofmann 2018)				
Responsible Conduct of Research Measure RCRM	Self-reported research misconduct and questionable research practices	42	6 point Likert scale		English	Social science researchers	Social science researchers	Principal component analysis Cronbach's alpha	High	High	Wester 2008	Available on request from first author

* Linked instruments listed consecutively and marked in green in this column

Table 4. Less-well-validated instruments

Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Issues in quality assessment	Reference
Knowledge, attitude, and practice toward plagiarism	24 close-ended 2 open-ended	Various	1. Knowledge 2. Attitude 3. Practice	Not stated, presumably Farsi/Persian	Journal editors	Reliability measured by Cronbach's alpha below 0.7	Abbasiyan et al 2018
"Research Ethics", not clearly defined	65	5 point Likert scale	1. Trustworthiness 2. Responsibility, 3. Professional commitment 4. Knowledge and information 5. Perseverance and patience 6. Observance of subject rights 7. Teamwork spirit 8. Responsibility to dissemination of results	Not stated, presumably Farsi/Persian	Medical researchers	Conceptual model / construct to be measured not clearly defined	Baleghi Damavandi et al 2019

Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Issues in quality assessment	Reference
			9. Attention to community needs				
Attitudes towards plagiarism, uses the Attitudes towards plagiarism questionnaire (ATPQ) (Mavrinac 2010)	29	5 point Likert scale		English	Doctoral students	Unclear whether plagiarism is understood as plagiarism in academic assignments, or as plagiarism in research publications	Farooq & Sultana 2022
Factors contributing to questionable research practice in publication	97	5 point Likert scale		English	Authors of scientific publications	Reliability not investigated	Gerrits et al 2020
Self-reported and firsthand observed research misconduct	22	Binary		English	Biomedical researchers in academia and industry	Reliability not investigated	Godecharle et al 2018

Construct(s) measured	Number of items	Response type	Sub-scales	Language	Intended respondent group(s)	Issues in quality assessment	Reference
Doctoral students' generic skills, including research integrity skills	21, but not clear how many relevant to research integrity skills	Not stated		English	Doctoral students	Response type and scoring rules not stated	Sakurai & Pyhältö 2021
Research ethics knowledge and analytical skills	41 Short version also described with 24 items	Binary true/false		English	Researchers and research students	No example items presented in paper Scoring rules not stated	Taylor et al 2012
Organizational climate for research integrity	43	Likert scale		English	Researchers and research students in academic health centers	Reliability not investigated	Thrush 2007

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Appendix A- PRISMA flowsheet

Appendix B – List of references for papers included in systematic review (with direct links)

* Indicates papers developing one or more scales and therefore included in this review of validated instruments

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